

A Study on Effective Performance Appraisal System in Eid Parry Nellikuppam

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ABSTRACT

In this dynamic and ever exponentially changing global market, nothing can be measured with accuracy because business world made market attributes volatile. In the complex business world, human beings are the most valuable assets. Human resources attitude is also volatile as subject to many experiences and situations. In such scenario, one needs to measure how Human Resources perform for the purpose of reward, assessment and knowledge. The tools and techniques innovated for measuring human productivity and performance with respect to the required capability, intellect and experience is under an umbrella named Performance Appraisal System. No single Performance Appraisal System can assure the reliability of its results. Performance appraisal system can only be performed as impartial as possible by choosing the best fit method out of trending ones. Performance appraisal is a continuous process to monitor the actual performance of the employee i.e. the work done by the employees throughout the year. In this stage careful selection of the appropriate techniques of measurement such as personal observation, statistical reports, and written reports for measuring the performance is needed. This paper attempts to explain performance appraisal system followed in EID parry sugar company nellikuppam.

KEYWORDS: Appraise, Appraiser, feedback, count, Performance Appraisal

I. INTRODUCTION

Edwin B, Flippo(1984) Performance appraisal is a systematic, periodic and so far as humanly possible, the impartial rating of an employee's excellence in matters pertaining to his present job and to his potentialities for a better job."

George (1986) refers to the appraisal systems in many organizations as "sterile paper chases". One possible reason for the widespread dissatisfaction with performance appraisal in organizations is that the systems used by organizations do not help them or their employees meet important goals.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Flaniken (2015) A challenge or pitfall in using a performance appraisal system is lack of leadership support for the process. Leadership refers to the top office in the university or college—The Office of the President. Strong support by leadership for the appraisal process is needed to help make the process beneficial. In the current study, 93.7% of the respondents said the leadership of their institution supported and encouraged the performance appraisal system at their college. If the responses to these questions are viewed in isolation, it would appear that there was very strong leadership support. However, the responses to two additional questions seemed to at least partially contradict this result. Another question asked if the amount of training provided to supervisors was sufficient.

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Joseph (2014) From the analyses of data collected, the following conclusions from our organization are studies are drawn: The appraisal system has been largely characterized by non-disclosure of appraisal result to the rates. This secrecy over performance appraisal results tends to put in the hands of supervisors and managers a potential tool for cracking down on "non-conforming subordinates with impunity.

Rusu, Huțu (2016) To conclude, the proposed model highlights the new trends in the field of employee performance appraisal, considering the strategic integration of human resources management, the role of the organizational context factors which influence the employee performance appraisal process, and performance criteria and standards customized in relation to the organizational context the employee performance appraisal is implemented. As a consequence, the proposed conceptual framework emphasizes the significant importance of a customized employee performance appraisal process in relation to the organizational context and employee job characteristics.

Rabenu and Tziner (2015) argue that performance appraisal should be individually customized "to fit both employees' specific jobs and their individual characteristics", and to be "appropriate to the constant changes in organizations' structure"

Ali & Opatha (2018) The results of the study lead to confirm the prediction made by the researchers regarding a significant and positive relationship between perceived systematic use of performance appraisal and perceived degree of business performance of apparel firms in Sri Lanka. It is more likely that an improvement of the quality of PA system of an apparel firm results in an improvement of business performance of the firm. No statistically significant differences exist between large apparel firms and non-large apparel firms with regard to perceived quality of PA and perceived degree of business performance. It is suggested Sri Lankan Journal of Human Resource Management Performance Appraisal System and 86 that future studies be carried out to test the validity of the second and third hypotheses by taking the two independent samples (large apparel firms and non-large apparel firms) which are similar exactly or approximately in terms of sample size.

Vincent Xavier (2015) Employee’s performance appraisal is necessary to the industry to achieve the goals of the industry. It is the duty of every organisation to give proper training and improve the efficiency of the employees in a better way. Employees are considered as the valuable assets of all organisations. The progress of the employees is closely linked with the performance. If the performance is improved obviously the quality of the organisation is improved. In way the performance appraisal system is an important factor to improve the quality of the employee as well as the industry. Here the study result clearly shown that the performance appraisal system of the particular industry is good and effective and have a high influence in the socio demographic factors.

III. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To find the effectiveness of performance appraisal at EID Parry, Nellikuppam
2. To find the satisfaction level of employees about the present system of performance appraisal.
3. To find the association between effectiveness of performance appraisal and employees’ job performance.

IV. HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

Ho: There is no association between effectiveness of performance appraisal and employees’ job performance.

V. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A research design is a plan that specifies the objectives of the study, method to be adopted in the data collection, tools in data analysis and hypothesis to be framed. The sample for the study is 50. The sampling technique followed in the study is simple random sampling. The study was based on both primary and secondary data. The primary data where collected from the employees working in EID PARRY. The statistical tool chi square is used in this study.

VI. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Performance Appraisal \ Job satisfaction	Low	Moderate	High
Low	0	0	0
Moderate	5	16	15
High	5	4	6

Source: primary data

The calculated value of chi square is 2.902 and the table value 9.488, p value is 0.574 > 0.05, H₀ is accepted. Therefore there is no significant association between effectiveness of performance appraisal and job satisfaction

VII. FINDING

As per the findings the effectiveness of performance appraisal is in moderate level, the level of satisfaction of the employees about the present system of performance appraisal is also moderate. Finally there is no association between the performance appraisal and employees job performance from the chi-square analysis.

VIII. SUGGESTION

Management have to identify the areas where the employee needs to improve upon in a professional development plan. Provide necessary suggestions if the employee is doing well and how they can improve to the next level.

1. Supervisors should try to setup a system for providing feedback on a weekly basis to their employees. Employees can use the performance review to see how they contribute and fit in to the company.
2. The company has to provide flexible working hours and opportunity to improve their skills and knowledge so that employees will have more involvement in their job.

CONCLUSION

According to Maurice, B. Coming, performance appraisal means “attempts to recognize and reward for personnel abilities that an individual brings to his job, measured by the extent to which his output or quality of his work exceeds the minimum that is fixed as the basic rate of pay”. The study has been conducted at ‘EID PARRY’ to find the satisfaction level of employee towards the existing performance appraisal system in the organization. It was concluded that the employees working in EID PARRY are not satisfied with the existing performance appraisal system, so the organization has to consider the opinion of employees before modify the system to evaluate the performance of employee’s.

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